

The Science of Lexplore

The method behind Lexplore was invented in January 2013 when we first applied machine learning to eye movement recordings to predict reading difficulties [1]. The initial dataset (i.e., eye movement recordings and reading outcomes) was from longitudinal research project on reading development and reading disability in Swedish school children running between 1989 and 2010. Using predictive modeling and statistical resampling techniques, we developed classification models that were able to differentiate high-risk subjects from low-risk subjects with a very high accuracy (> 95%) based on less than one minute of reading [3].

Eye tracking has long been used to investigate reading and cognitive processes. However, it is only in recent years that it has become possible to do eye tracking outside of the lab, on large number of students, and to analyze the results using artificial intelligence. We have performed two large research studies [9, 20] and several validation experiments [4, 13, 14, 19, 30] to verify the accuracy, validity, and reliability of the method (figure 1). Other research groups have reported similar findings using eye tracking and machine learning [2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 15, 16, 17, 18, 22, 26, 28]. Our reported results have also been independently replicated by other researchers [22, 24, 27]. More recently, a few systematic reviews of the research have also been published [21, 25, 29].

Figure 1. Timeline of the research behind Lexplore from 1989 to today with studies, milestones, models, and publications (the numbers correspond to the list of references).

In the first research study (2014-2015) where we developed the methodology and procedure for screening in schools used by Lexplore, we recorded eye movements on 3,444 Swedish students in grade 1-3. Of these, 1,236 students were screened twice one year apart. In this study, we did not know which children that had reading difficulties, instead we performed a traditional screening inventory involving word segmentation, rapid naming, pseudo-word, and sight-word reading. A composite score of the traditional inventory was then used as the outcome variable for training and evaluating models for each grade. The results showed that our method achieved an accuracy of 86 % with a balanced sensitivity (85 %) and specificity (88 %) when classifying students at-risk [9].

When we launched Lexplore in Spring 2017, we used the models from the first research study in grade 1-3 and presented the results as the number of students at risk or not. However, as we now had data from a large sample of students, we next developed a model where we predict the percentile score of reading ability rather than if the student is below or above a threshold. The new regression-based model, which also took oral and silent reading modes into account, achieved a correlation of $R^2 = 78\%$ across grade 1-3 between observed versus predicted standard scores [9]. In Spring 2017, we validated the model for English in the US by comparing our results to DIBELS ($n=177$), FAST ($n=130$) and STAR ($n=123$). The results showed a consistent agreement between the tests with an accuracy of on average 91% although the thresholds for at-risk varied between the tests [30].

In the second research study (2018-2019), we collaborated with University of Memphis and screened 1,484 students in grade 1-8 at schools in California in Fall, Winter, and Spring [4]. Lexplore was incorporated into the standard benchmark battery concurrent with the i-Ready assessment. Oral Reading Fluency (ORF) was assessed for all screenings at UoM by trained research assistants. Based on the data we developed a new model that used running records ORF as the outcome measure for training and evaluation. Norms for the grade and periods were adopted from Hasbrouck & Tindal (2017) which incorporates data from 6,7 million ORF assessments [31]. Predictive validity was assessed by comparing the results from Lexplore and i-Ready to the end-of-year state test used in California (CAASPP, Smarter Balance) for grade 3-8.

Our latest model based on the second study achieves an accuracy of 97% compared to the ORF measure across grades 1-8 (Figure 2). The model has a test-retest reliability of 85% (assessed by testing the same group of students on week apart). The concurrent correlation between Lexplore and i-Ready was $r = .75$. The correlation between the end-of-year state tests and Lexplore was $.65$ in both spring and fall, the results for ORF were similar. The correlation between the CAASPP and i-Ready benchmarks were $.80$ in fall and $.85$ in spring. The result on the California end-of-year state tests was used as cut-off for predictive analysis (standard met or exceeded). Fall benchmarks for Lexplore, ORF and i-Ready was analyzed using ROC curve analyses. The area under the curve (AUC) for fall benchmarks ($n = 927$) were $.79$ for Lexplore, $.81$ for ORF, and $.83$ for i-Ready. These results clearly demonstrate the concurrent and predictive validity of Lexplore [4].

Figure 2. Accuracy of our latest model (V5) in grades 1-8 ($R^2 = .97$, $p < .001$). Predicted ORF score is plotted on the x-axis and actual ORF score on the y-axis.

The analysis using our latest model (V6 - see table 1) is divided into three steps: The first step predicts the words correct per minute ratio for the oral and silent reading, the second step calculates the percentile score based on a combination of the Hasbrouck & Tindal norms and the previous recordings we have in the system (currently about 400,000). In the third and final step, scores are balanced against the results on the comprehension questions. The norms are adjusted independently for the supported languages (Swedish, US English, UK English Norwegian, and Portuguese). Given the large number of previous recordings we have aggregated over time, we can now provide norms with a weekly granularity of reading development. This approach enables Lexplore to produce relative (percentiles) and absolute (composites) scores that accurately reflects the dynamics in reading development across the academic year as well as through the grades.

Table 1. Comparison of recent analysis models used by Lexplore with incremental improvements.

	V2	V3	V4	V5	V6
	Aug 2017	Aug 2018	Jan 2019	Jan 2020	Jan 2021
Grades	1 - 3 in spring, 2 - 4 in fall	1 - 4	1 - 6	1 - 9	1 - 12
Languages	Swedish, US English	Swedish, US English, UK English	Swedish, US English, UK English	Swedish, US English, UK English, Norwegian, Portuguese	Swedish, English (UK, US, ANZ), Norwegian, Portuguese, German
Target	Standard score of composites based on reference tests. Swedish research study	Standard score of composites based on reference tests. Swedish research study	Oral Reading Fluency. US research project	Oral Reading Fluency US research project	Oral Reading Fluency and Comprehension scores. US research project.
Modality	Oral and silent reading mode used as a feature in the model	Oral and silent reading mode used as a feature in the model	Oral and silent reading mode used as a feature in the model	Separate models for oral and silent reading	Separate models for oral and silent reading
Granularity	One distribution per semester	One distribution per month	One distribution per month	One distribution per week	One distribution per week
Strength	Well established targets as measure for reading skills	Enabled progress monitoring as it had monthly norms	Well established norms for oral reading ability, easier to adapt new languages	Handles aloud and silent separately with high accuracy, improved reliability	Takes comprehension into account, improved norms in lower grades
Model sample size	4866	4866	2594	2594	2594
Norm sample size	4866	17 353	6,7 million + 35 389	6,7 million + 212 529	6,7 million + 410 292
Accuracy	79 %	79 %	95 %	97 %	97 %
Reliability	n/a	82 %	65 %	85 %	tbd

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